

The Role of Mirror Neurons and Affective-Sensory-Motor Synchrony Between Mother and Baby in the Pathophysiology of Some Forms of Developmental Dysphasia in Children

Marcelo Caixeta

Psychiatrist, Federal University of Goiás – Brazil

ORCID: 0000-0003-2357-6558

E-mail: psychological.medicine1@gmail.com

Abstract

This paper proposes a new pathophysiological approach to developmental language disorders in childhood, focusing on the function of mirror neurons and the formation of the "secondary self" through affective-motor synchrony between mother and baby. Based on the analysis of a clinical case of expressive phonological-syntactic dysphasia with specific anomia for compound nouns, the limitations of classic lesional neurological models and the need for a psychiatric and functional interpretation are discussed. Mirror neuron deficiency compromises internal language, working memory, sensory-motor feedback, and consequently, the construction of semantics, concepts, and the lexicon. The model is articulated with the classifications of Rapin, Crosson, Christophe, Loic, and Gérard, culminating in a therapeutic proposal based on psychiatric pathophysiology and Vygotsky's historical-cultural theory. The role of psychiatry in the diagnosis and treatment of these disorders, traditionally relegated to neurology and speech-language pathology, is emphasized.

Keywords: Developmental dysphasia in children; Mirror neuron; Internal language; Working memory; Developmental psychiatry; Lexicon and semantics; Vygotsky-based therapy.

1. Introduction: A New Approach to Developmental Language Disorders

This paper proposes an alternative approach to the classic adult neurology model for explaining psychiatric developmental cognitive disorders, especially those involving receptive, expressive, written, and reading language.

The traditional model posits that specific lesions—for example, in Broca's or Wernicke's area—generate corresponding linguistic syndromes. However, this paradigm may be inadequate to explain developmental dysfunctions in children, such as dysphasias, dyslexias, or dyscalculias. An alternative, psychiatric and functional paradigm is proposed here, centered on mirror neuron dysfunction and its relationship with the formation of the "secondary self" during mother-baby interaction.

2. Clinical Case Study: Expressive Dysphasia with Anomia for Compound Nouns

We present the case of an eight-year-old boy referred for child psychiatric evaluation with a prior diagnosis of autism spectrum disorder (ASD) and attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD). However, the evaluation revealed it to be an expressive phonological-syntactic dysphasia with a very specific clinical manifestation: marked difficulty in naming compound nouns.

While simple nouns like "ball" or "dog" were named appropriately, compound expressions such as "ironing board" caused significant blocks. This is a form of anomia restricted to more semantically loaded words, pointing to a failure that is not only lexical but, above all, semantic and motor. This clinical picture prompted a conceptual review of the role of mirror neurons in language development.

3. Mirror Neurons and the Formation of Internal Language: A Psychophysiological Hypothesis

In children with psychiatric developmental disorders—often included within the spectrum of general psychiatric syndrome [1]—a recurrent association is observed between hyperactivity, difficulties in social context processing, and mirror neuron dysfunction.

During early mother-baby interaction, a fundamental phenomenon for language acquisition occurs: the mother names the baby's gestures, emotions, and intentions, thus building an affective-sensory proto-syntax. For example, when the baby cries, the mother might say, "You're crying because your teddy bear fell on the floor." This act of naming associates a motor behavior with a linguistic structure. Under normal conditions, the child internalizes this language through the activation of mirror neurons, progressively developing their internal language, which will then accompany their own actions.

However, in children with functional mirror neuron deficiency, this internalization is impaired. The subject may exhibit difficulties ranging from repeating words to complete failure in formulating complex sentences. The absence of a "secondary self"—a reflexive instance that converses with itself—prevents the development of fluid language, leading to short, telegraphic speech.

4. Relationship Between Mirror Neurons, Semantics, and Lexicon

Mirror neuron deficiency compromises the feedback mechanism necessary to control complex motor acts such as speech. A striking example is that of a child who finds it easier to articulate syllables like "MA" (more physiological) but struggles with syllables like "AM," whose production requires greater phonological motor control. This was observed in the patient under study, who could not correctly repeat words with "AM," demonstrating a failure in the proprioceptive monitoring of the articulatory gesture.

This deficit extends to the semantic plane. Objects with high semantic load, such as "ironing board," are more difficult to name than simple nouns. This occurs because the child, without a well-formed "secondary self," cannot describe to themselves the uses, functions, and contexts of that object. As a consequence, conceptual construction fails, compromising the formation of the lexicon. The concept—as a summary of semantics—does not consolidate, and the lexicon does not become fixed.

This feedback deficit affects not only the naming of complex objects but also the ability to maintain a continuous line of reasoning. Language, in this context, becomes a fine motor act that requires precise sensory-motor control, sustained by a well-structured internal dialogue. For psychiatric pathophysiological interpretations of dysphasias, refer to [2-5].

5. Implications for Working Memory and Telegraphic Language

Working memory—understood here as the ability to maintain an internal discursive line—critically depends on the quality of internal language. In patients with mirror neuron dysfunction, this internal language is poor, fragmented, and short. The subject cannot "talk to themselves" continuously and effectively, which impairs the syntactic articulation of long sentences, mathematical problem-solving, and causal logical reasoning.

Speech becomes reduced, with automatic phrases, verbal inertia, or telegraphic discourse. Sentences constructed with syntactic elaboration, logical sequencing, or causal relationships become unfeasible, given the impairment in internal elaboration. The child begins to operate with frozen or mimetic language, often characterized by isolated nouns ("little foot, doggy, silly") instead of articulated utterances with verbs, adverbs, and connectors.

Figure 1: Diagram of the pathophysiology of developmental dysphasia in children.

6. Classifications of Dysphasias in Childhood: Contributions from Rapin, Crosson, and Gérard/Le Hewzey (Herold Hospital School)

Various authors have proposed classificatory models for developmental dysphasias in childhood. Below, three main lines are highlighted, proposed by Isabelle Rapin, by Crosson, and by the French school led by Christophe-Loic Gérard/M.F. Le Hewzey.

6.1 Isabelle Rapin's Classification

Isabelle Rapin proposed a model based on five main syndromes of linguistic dysfunction in child development [6]:

- * **Auditory Agnosia:** Severe verbal comprehension disorders, with difficulty in phonemic discrimination. Syntax is rudimentary or nonexistent, although the desire to communicate is present. There is a dissociation between verbal performance and intellectual potential, and behavioral disorders occur when the severity of comprehension is underestimated.
- * **Semantic-Pragmatic Syndrome:** Involves impairment in language comprehension and use. Speech is fluent, which can create a false impression of normality. The child may repeat phrases or television jingles but uses inappropriate words in spontaneous speech and exhibits thought incoherence. Behavioral disorders are frequent, and hydrocephalus is a common etiology.

- * Infantile Autism: Included by Rapin as an entity with its own linguistic manifestations, often coexisting with the previous syndromes.
- * Mixed Phonological-Syntactic Syndrome: Preserved or near-normal comprehension, but with reduced expression, phonetic facilitation, and rudimentary syntax. Bucco-facial apraxia or pseudobulbar signs may exist, as well as graphomotor difficulties.
- * Phonetic Programming Deficit Syndrome: Expression is poor or absent, with normal comprehension. In one variant, speech is practically null; in the other, there is expressive effort with such intense distortions that intelligibility is null. Ferry et al. call this condition verbal apraxia, comparable to aphemia [6].

6.2 Gérard/Le Hewzey (Herold-Paris) Classification

This classification was developed based on similarities with adult aphasias [7, 8]:

- * Group I: Normal or slightly impaired verbal comprehension, reduced and agrammatical verbal expression, and bucco-facial gesturing disorders. Equivalent to Broca's aphasia.
- * Group II: Inability to repeat verbal or non-verbal sequences, with paraphasias and anomia. Similarity to conduction aphasia.
- * Group III: Impairment in both verbal and non-verbal decoding, with paraphasias and dyssyntax. Approaches sensory or Wernicke's aphasia.
- * Group IV: Massive impairment in encoding and decoding, similar to global aphasia, often associated with left-handedness or ambidexterity.
- * Group V: Moderately impaired decoding, with compromised lexical evocation and weak memory. Resembles mnemonic disorders.

6.3 Additional Contributions from Crosson

Although less frequently cited in Portuguese literature, Crosson also proposed that different types of linguistic dysfunction in childhood reflect varied combinations of deficits in reception, semantic processing, phonological formulation, and motor programming, reinforcing the multifactorial nature of these dysfunctions [9].

7. Mirror Neuron Dysfunction as a Central Axis

Among the various types of dysphasia, mirror neuron dysfunction in the posterior parietal region stands out as a primary mechanism in many developmental forms of childhood language dysfunction. This region is implicated in articulatory proprioception and the ability to control one's own speech. Children with this dysfunction do not precisely feel what they articulate, which compromises phonological and syntactic control.

The failure can extend to the connection bundles between the posterior sensory areas and the anterior motor programming areas, hindering the transport of proprioceptive information for phonological formulation. This model is compatible with the type of adult conduction aphasia and with many pediatric clinical presentations.

For example, in developmental dyslexias associated with these conditions, greater difficulty is observed in articulating phonemes requiring proprioceptive control (such as "AM") compared to simpler phonemes (such as "MA"). This indicates a functional sensorimotor deficit and not merely an articulatory one.

8. Therapeutic Implications and Clinical Discussion

Therapy in these cases must necessarily be based on the underlying pathophysiology. As in any area of medicine, therapeutic prescription depends on a precise understanding of the mechanisms involved. In the case of developmental dysphasia in children, speech therapy treatments are usually based on isolated phonological or articulatory models, often derived from adult neurological conditions. Such approaches, although valid in certain contexts, may not be adequate for dysfunctions with an essentially psychiatric and functional etiology, as observed in this clinical case.

In this specific case, the patient was undergoing speech therapy focused on punctual phonological corrections, such as distinguishing homophonous words ("tatu" and "tato"). However, as demonstrated, the core of the dysfunction lay in a broader deficit, involving the failure to form a "secondary self," mediated by mirror neuron dysfunction, which compromised internal language, working memory, semantics, and, secondarily, the lexicon and syntax.

8.1 The Psychiatric Proposal of Vygotsky's Re-educational Model

According to Vygotsky's principles, preserved functions should be reinforced and used as a basis to compensate for those that are deficient [10]. Applying this model to the case in question, it was observed that the patient presented some preserved lexical anchors. This allows the use of the available vocabulary as "fixed pictures" in the child's mind, from which chained narratives—a semantic "film sequence"—can be constructed.

For this purpose, strategies are suggested, such as:

- * Using sequential comic strips, with cutting and reorganization;
- * Oral retelling of stories, promoting vocal elongation and syntactic enrichment;
- * Expanding vocabulary with verbs, adverbs, and connectors;
- * Working with discursive functions (function words) for narrative structuring.

8.2 Emotional Synchronization and Affective Language

Treatment should also consider the affective synchronization between the child and the therapist. The naming of actions and emotions by the therapist (as the mother originally did) should be gradually returned to the child. The child should learn to name the adult's actions and, progressively, to describe their own emotions and thoughts. This can be done with:

- * Interactive turn-taking games (shared drawing in Winnicott's squiggle style);
- * Activities with face photos and videos with emotional expression;
- * Joint attention, prosody, and theory of mind training;
- * Interventions that promote fluency, causality, and continuity of discourse.

This approach favors the formation of a verbalizing secondary self, which reorganizes internal discourse and improves the child's linguistic and attentional performance.

9. Final Considerations: For a Psychiatry of Linguistic Development

This paper proposes a paradigm shift in the approach to childhood dysphasias, moving away from the neurological lesional tradition and closer to a psychiatric and neurofunctional interpretation. The conditions described here cannot be reduced to isolated motor dysfunctions but must be understood as failures in the symbolic and reflective development of the subject, anchored in the initial interaction with the other, mediated by mirror neurons.

The described case illustrates how late diagnosis, the absence of early psychiatric evaluation, and adherence to restrictive speech therapy models contribute to the persistence of significant deficits. An integrated pathophysiological, psychodynamic, and linguistic approach allows for a deeper understanding and more effective rehabilitation of patients with complex language dysfunctions.

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